

Exploring why and how commercial organizations contribute to OpenStreetMap

Héctor Ochoa-Ortiz & Barbara Re

To cite this article: Héctor Ochoa-Ortiz & Barbara Re (06 Feb 2025): Exploring why and how commercial organizations contribute to OpenStreetMap, Annals of GIS, DOI: [10.1080/19475683.2025.2457396](https://doi.org/10.1080/19475683.2025.2457396)

To link to this article: <https://doi.org/10.1080/19475683.2025.2457396>

© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Informa UK Limited, trading as Taylor & Francis Group, on behalf of Nanjing Normal University.

Published online: 06 Feb 2025.

Submit your article to this journal [↗](#)

Article views: 90

View related articles [↗](#)

View Crossmark data [↗](#)

Exploring why and how commercial organizations contribute to OpenStreetMap

Héctor Ochoa-Ortiz

Computer Science Division, School of Science and Technology, Università degli Studi di Camerino, Camerino, Italy

ABSTRACT

OpenStreetMap (OSM) is a Digital Commons platform, collaboratively developed, and centred on creating an accurate spatial representation of the world. Its flexibility and open nature have attracted multiple commercial organizations to use data from and contribute to the platform in several ways. This study examines the motivations and methods of commercial organizations to contribute to OSM, based on semi-structured interviews with employees of 25 commercial organizations and the Overture Maps Foundation. Five distinct ways of contribution have been found: data editing, tool development and/or funding, event sponsoring, OSM Foundation or related funding, and community building. The motivations behind their contribution to the project are a mixture of their own business benefits, such as to improve the data quality in a source the companies use, and social value motivations, like community-building. Commercial organizations have also encountered barriers with OSM in its use and contribution, ultimately resulting in the recent development of the Overture Maps platform. OSM should, in turn, provide a space where those self-motivations can be turned into social good and, at the same time, achieve an inviting space for all stakeholders (including commercial organizations) to ensure project sustainability, without falling into the tragedy of the commons.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received 31 July 2024
Accepted 8 January 2025

KEYWORDS

Digital commons;
OpenStreetMap; commercial
organizations; motivations

1. Introduction

When volunteers come together to fill in the gap in the availability of digital geographical information, for example, when similar commercial platforms do not exist, it can be considered Volunteered Geographical Information (VGI) (Goodchild 2007). OpenStreetMap (OSM), a global geographic information database, has become the most renowned example of VGI and has achieved a whole ecosystem of tools and stakeholders around it, with a great potential research field emerging from it (Grinberger et al. 2022, 2023). OSM, however, provides a playing field that has enabled not only individuals but also organizational actors (profit and non-profit) to take a role in the project (Schröder-Bergen 2023).

In this paper, we explore how and why commercial organizations are both using and contributing to the project. The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 presents the literature concerning OSM, its governance, organizational and commercial entities related to the project, and finally how it relates to Spatial Data Infrastructures (SDIs). Section 3 specifies the methodology followed, and describes the interviewed organizations. In Section 4, we analyse the results from different perspectives: why and how are they using OSM, how are they contributing, and what are their motivations to do so, strengths and

weaknesses reported by the interviewees, and how do the companies react to the imposed barriers. Section 5 discusses the findings, and Section 6 concludes the paper and proposes future work.

2. Previous work

2.1. OpenStreetMap and its governance

OSM is supported by the OSM Foundation (OSMF), a non-profit organization that maintains and develops the infrastructure where OSM runs. The OSMF is subdivided into the Board of Directors (who manage the foundation and get elected), the Advisory Board (a group of individuals the Board of Directors may ask for advice), Local Chapters (non-profit legal entities representing a country or region recognized by the OSMF), Working Groups (which support the work in different key areas of the project), and Committees and other groups. The OSMF has three types of membership: Normal member (natural person, voting rights), associate member (natural person, most voting rights) and corporate member (companies and organizations, no voting rights). Despite having no voting rights, corporate members can have a seat on the Advisory Board, for Bronze-level corporate members

CONTACT Héctor Ochoa-Ortiz hector.ochoaortiz@unicam.it

or higher. Local chapters can also each have a seat at the OSMF Advisory board (OpenStreetMap Wiki 2023). Even if commercial organizations do not have direct voting rights, individuals who work for companies do not have restrictions to become OSMF members and can be elected to the Board of Directors, with debates emerging around the role employees of major tech companies play in OSM (Schröder-Bergen et al. 2022).

Governance literature has focused mostly on government initiatives, paying little attention to open governance initiatives by non-government actors that solve societal problems, where OSM is a great case study where this happens (Park, Longo, and Johnston 2020).

Given its governance and co-creation practices, being a freely available community-managed resource, OSM can be considered a Data Commons (Pollet 2022; Schröder-Bergen 2023). How to manage the shared resources in a commons, and achieve a balance between the interests of the stakeholders, including commercial entities, and have an understanding between them, which is key for ensuring the sustainability of the project (Cazacu et al. 2024; Schröder-Bergen 2023).

Park, Longo, and Johnston (2020) developed a conceptual model from the case of OSM to understand open governance initiatives. They found three themes for the model: environment, process, and results. In the environment theme, they state the external partnerships with different organizations the project has managed (with governmental organizations, NGOs, and commercial organizations) for satellite imagery donation and funding (e.g. OSMF corporate members). In the process, they mention volunteerism, coordination (based on commons-based peer production and micro-tasking), technology (diverse and fitting for different cases), outreach and training, and decentralization as the driving sub-themes. Finally, for the results, they note the outputs (data) and outcomes (non-data values, e.g. community empowerment) achieved for the project.

2.2. (Open) spatial data infrastructures

A Spatial Data Infrastructure (SDI) is defined as ‘the technology, policies, standards, human resources, and related activities necessary to acquire, process, distribute, use, maintain, and preserve spatial data’ (Office of Management and Budget 2002).

There have been efforts over the years to make SDIs more open, with stakeholders such as commercial users, citizens, and other non-governmental entities becoming key actors, in contrast to the more traditional focus on

public authorities only (Vancauwenberghe and van Loenen 2018).

Spinoza Andreo et al.’s research focuses on assessing the motivations and user perspective of OSM, aligning it with previous literature on SDI and Open Data Ecosystems (Spinoza Andreo 2022; Spinoza Andreo, Welle Donker, and Calzati 2023). The work centres on individual instead of organizational or institutional collaboration but recognizes OSM as fulfilling the Open SDI definitions, with the interviewees agreeing on considering OSM an Open Data Ecosystem.

The International Cartographic Association mentions six main stakeholder types that can appear in SDIs: Policy Maker, Producer, Provider, Broker, Value-added Reseller, and End User (Cooper et al. 2023). This paper aims to link these types to the role commercial users take using and collaborating in OSM, based on the VGI-Extended SDI stakeholder model (Cooper et al. 2011).

2.3. Organizational and commercial OSM

Previous research in commercial OpenStreetMap has been centred around three main topics, explained below.

Anderson and Sarkar have comprehensively researched corporate editing in OSM by identifying paid editors and corporate editing patterns inside the database. This has been done by collating a list of corporate editors and extracting their edits from the changesets. In recent years, companies have hired paid editors to improve OSM data, and their importance in data editing has been increasing over time. They also state the difficulty of creating such a corporate contributor list, due to the variety in how each organization documents their edits online (Anderson 2021; Anderson and Sarkar 2020; Anderson, Sarkar, and Palen 2019; Sarkar and Anderson 2022; Veselovsky et al. 2022).

Schröder-Bergen et al. have studied the (de-)colonization practices present in OSM. According to their research, edits have shifted from mostly individuals from the Global North to a mixture of individual and institutional actors (both profit and non-profit) with broader global coverage in recent years. This can result in increased stakeholder cooperation but can also lead to conflict when organizations fail to understand the local context and the OSM dynamics (Michel and Schröder-Bergen 2022; Schröder-Bergen 2023; Schröder-Bergen et al. 2022).

Yang et al. have studied how the contributions of organizations (both profit and non-profit) affect the data inequality in OSM, complementing Schröder-Bergen et al.’s work. They deeply analysed the edits of 9 selected big organizations and concluded that between 2015 and 2020, they have played a big role

in reducing the data inequality between countries, with non-profit organizations playing a bigger role than for-profit ones, with the notable exception of corporations with a humanitarian vision (Yang et al. 2024).

The impact commercial organizations can have on OSM has been studied in different ways. However, the literature lacks a study of the needs, motivations, and barriers to contributing to OSM from the commercial actors' perspective.

We therefore propose the following research questions: How are commercial organizations using OSM data? How are commercial organizations contributing value to the OSM Ecosystem? What motivates and hinders them to do so? What strengths and weaknesses do commercial organizations see in OSM?

3. Methodology

We conducted semi-structured interviews that allowed us to ask in-depth, open-ended questions to interviewees directly related to the research questions (Jamshed 2014). We contacted companies listed on the OSM Wiki Organised Editing page (OpenStreetMap Wiki 2024), as well as those in the OSMF Corporate Members list (OpenStreetMap Foundation 2024b). Personal contacts from the authors and people proposed by the interviewees at the end of the interview were also contacted. The final list of interviewees can be seen in Table 1, with

its geographical distribution in Figure 1(a). The interviews were done between November 2023 and February 2024. We managed to interview 11.9% (5/42) of the for-profit organizations listed in (OpenStreetMap Wiki 2024) and 38.6% (17/44) of those listed on the OSMF website (OpenStreetMap Foundation 2024b). Five of the interviewed commercial organizations, and the Overture Maps Foundation, were in neither list.

We can see that the Global North dominates the commercial landscape of OSM when it comes to countries of their headquarters, both on the OSM Wiki Organised Editing page (OpenStreetMap Wiki 2024) — see Figure 1(b) and Table 2— and the OSMF Corporate Members list (OpenStreetMap Foundation 2024b) —see Figure 1(c) and Table 3—, with two countries that stand out: the United States of America, and Germany. A big cluster of companies can be seen in the European continent, with a smaller cluster appearing in South and South-East Asia (India-Singapore-Indonesia). There could still be commercial contributors that do not document their contributions and, therefore, are difficult to find.

This is in stark contrast to humanitarian and non-profit efforts: HOT edits and YouthMappers location chapters, which are mostly located in the Global South (Schröder-Bergen et al. 2022). This could indicate a divide in how organized editing is done globally.

The interviews were done through an online video call 30–60 minutes long, except when technical

Table 1. Interviewed organizations, ordered alphabetically.

Organization name	Org. type	Org. domain	Org. HQs	Interviewee(s)	Int. based in
<i>Asamm Software</i>	SME	App dev., GIS	Czechia	2 employees	Czechia
<i>Bunting Labs</i>	SME	AI, GIS	USA	Co-founder	USA
<i>Con.sens Verkehrsplanung</i>	SME	Urban Planning	Austria	Shareholder	Austria
<i>Elastic</i>	Big corp.	IT	Netherlands	Employee	Spain
<i>Esri</i>	Big corp.	GIS	USA	Employee	USA
<i>Farmeye</i>	SME	Agriculture, GIS	Ireland	Co-founder	Ireland
<i>Geofabrik</i>	SME	GIS	Germany	Co-founder	Germany
<i>Gojek (GoTo)</i>	Big corp.	Various, IT	Indonesia	2 employees	Indonesia
<i>Graphhopper</i>	SME	Routing services	Germany	Co-founder	Germany
<i>Interline Technologies</i>	SME	Mobility, GIS	USA	Co-founder	USA
<i>Intevation</i>	SME	IT	Germany	Co-Founder	Germany
<i>Kontur</i>	SME	GIS	USA	Employee	Poland
<i>MapToolkit</i>	SME	Cartography, GIS	Austria	Founder	Austria
<i>Meta Platforms</i>	Big corp.	Social networks, IT	USA	Employee	UK
<i>MobilityLabel</i>	SME	Mobility, GIS	Netherlands	Co-founder	Netherlands
<i>OpenCage</i>	SME	Geocoding	Germany	Co-founder	Germany
<i>Overture Maps Foundation</i>	Foundation	GIS	USA	CEO	USA
<i>Plan4Better</i>	SME	GIS	Germany	CEO	Germany
<i>Protomaps</i>	SME	GIS	USA	Founder	USA
<i>Rinkai</i>	SME	Mobility, GIS	Czechia	2 Employees	Czechia
<i>Stadia Maps</i>	SME	Cartography, GIS	USA	Co-founder	South Korea
<i>StreetLight Data</i>	Big corp. ¹	GIS, Mobility	USA	CTO	USA
<i>TEconecta</i>	SME	Telecommunications	Spain	Co-founder	Spain
<i>Thunderforest (Gravitystorm)</i>	SME	Cartography, GIS	UK	Founder	UK
<i>TomTom</i>	Big corp.	Mobility, GIS	Netherlands	Employee	Netherlands
<i>VK</i>	Big corp.	Social networks, IT	Russia	Several employees	Russia

SME: small and medium-sized enterprise (<250 employees).

(a) Organizations contacted by headquarters location, and interviewed employee(s) location. See table 1

(b) For-profit organizations in the OSM Wiki Organised Editing page (OpenStreetMap Wiki 2024) by headquarters location. See table 2

(c) OSMF for-profit Corporate Members (OpenStreetMap Foundation 2024b) by headquarters location. See table 3

Figure 1. Commercial organizations location.2

Table 2. For-profit organizations in the OSM wiki organised editing page (OpenStreetMap Wiki 2024) by headquarters location.

Country	Number of organizations
USA	16
Germany	6
India	3
Iran, UK	2
Australia, Austria, Belarus, Canada, Czechia, Estonia, Moldavia, Netherlands, Russia, Singapore, Sweden, Switzerland, Zambia	1

Table 3. Corporate members of the OSMF (OpenStreetMap Foundation 2024b) by headquarters location and membership level.

Country	Total number	Platinum	Gold	Silver	Bronze	Supporter
USA	11	1	3	3	3	1
Germany	11	0	2	3	5	1
Netherlands	3	1	0	1	0	1
Singapore	2	0	1	1	0	0
Estonia	2	0	0	1	1	0
Austria	2	0	0	0	0	2
Indonesia	1	0	1	0	0	0
Canada, Cyprus, Czechia, France, Russia	1	0	0	0	1	0
Belgium, Denmark, India, Ireland, Sweden, Switzerland, UK	1	0	0	0	0	1
Not-for-profit, HQs location not considered	4	0	0	2	0	2

problems or availability of the interviewee did not allow to do so, asking the interviewees to send the answer in text form in those rare cases. We transcribed the interviewees' answers and used those notes to extract conclusions in the following Section 4.

The most relevant questions asked to the interviewees regarding this paper results are 'Does your organization use OpenStreetMap? How?', 'Does your organization contribute to OSM? Why? How?', 'What is the motivation for your organization to contribute to OSM?', 'Are there any barriers to the contribution?', and 'Can you describe the main strengths and weaknesses of OSM?'. Other questions were asked to provide context to the answers, as well as questions whose answers were ultimately not included in this paper. Appendix A contains the complete list of questions asked to the interviewees.

4. Results

The results are separated into five subsections. The first subsection explains the reasons (why) stated by the interviewed commercial organizations for using OSM data. The second subsection explains the methods (how) in which commercial organizations contribute value to the OSM Ecosystem, mapping the contributions to the VGI-extended SDI stakeholder model. The third subsection explains the motivations and barriers commercial organizations encounter to contribute to the OSM Ecosystem. The fourth subsection explains the strengths and weaknesses commercial organizations see in OSM. Finally, the fifth subsection introduces the Overture Maps project and how it relates to the barriers commercial organizations encounter when using and contributing to OSM.

4.1. Why and how are commercial organizations using OSM data

We asked the interviewees the following question: 'Does your organization use OpenStreetMap? How?'. In their response, most participants also explained in detail why

their companies use OSM as a data source. We identified three main reasons for using OSM data from commercial organizations, which are described below.

4.1.1. Quality combined with open license

Interviewees highlighted the good quality of OSM's data, together with the ability to reuse it freely, as key reasons for its commercial use. A participant mentioned OSM's data quality as the second best in the market, with Google Maps being the first. This is complemented by several interviewees who mentioned the expensive cost of using Google Maps data and the inability to use their data outside of their API as reasons to use OSM. OSM allows commercial users to download and reuse data to their liking, and adapt it to their project needs.

4.1.2. One-stop shop

Some companies compare the use of OSM to other open sources, like Open Government Data (OGD). OGD usually comes in different formats and sources, with no platform combining them into one. That makes OGD, even if rich in quality, not commercially profitable to use if the companies operate or offer their services across different jurisdictions and, therefore, have to deal with multiple data sources or if no specific tooling exists to handle a given specific dataset, and own tools need to be developed. OSM provides companies with a one-stop shop for getting their data.

4.1.3. Community

A common theme mentioned among those interviewed was the community. A vibrant community that maintains the data and builds tools around it allows companies to focus more resources on the services they offer instead of allocating resources to collect data from scratch. Depending on the use case and domain, companies either use OSM exclusively or merge it with other sources, including their own sources, to provide a service that fits their needs. Most companies are, therefore, considered value-added resellers according to the SDI stakeholder roles, explained in detail later in the paper (section 4.2, Table 5).

4.2. How are commercial organizations contributing to OSM – not only data

Five main ways of contributing have been identified. Apart from data contribution (OSM Database editing), more researched in the field, commercial users can also contribute value to OSM in other ways: tool development in the OSM ecosystem (whether with assigned

developers, pull requests or financial funding to software projects), OSM Foundation or other OSM-related non-profit funding (e.g. local chapters, HOT), event sponsoring (mostly State of the Map branded events, but also other local events), and finally community building. The ways each company contributes value are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Contribution ways.

Organization name	DE	TO	NF	ES	CB
<i>Asamm Software</i>	X				
<i>Bunting Labs</i>		X			
<i>Con.sens Verkehrsplanung</i>	X		X		
<i>Elastic</i>		X	X	X	
<i>Esri</i>	³	X	X	X	
<i>Farmeye</i>			X		
<i>Geofabrik</i>	X ⁴	X	X	X	X
<i>Gojek (GoTo)</i>			X	X	X
<i>Graphhopper</i>		X	X		
<i>Interline Technologies</i>		X	X		
<i>Intevation</i>		X	X		
<i>Kontur</i>	X	X			X
<i>MapToolkit</i>	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Meta Platforms</i>	X	X	X	X	X
<i>MobilityLabel</i>	X	X	X		
<i>OpenCage</i>		X	X		X
<i>Plan4Better</i>	X				X
<i>Protomaps</i>	X ⁵				
<i>Rinkai</i>	X		X		
<i>Stadia Maps</i>		X	X	X	
<i>StreetLight Data</i>	X ⁶				
<i>TEconecta</i>	X				
<i>Thunderforest (Gravitystorm)</i>		X			
<i>TomTom</i>	X	X	X	X	X
<i>VK</i>	X ⁷	X	X	X ⁸	X ⁸

DE: OSM database editing, TO: tool development and/or funding, NF: OSMF or other OSM related NGOs funding, ES: event sponsoring, CB: community building.

Table 5. SDI stakeholder roles taken by each company in relation to OSM, as resulting from interviews.

Organization name	PM	Pd	Pv	Br	VAR	EU
<i>Asamm Software</i>		X	X		X	
<i>Bunting Labs</i>				X		X
<i>Con.sens Verkehrsplanung</i>		X			X	X
<i>Elastic</i>	X				X	
<i>Esri</i>	X			X	X	
<i>Farmeye</i>					X	X
<i>Geofabrik</i>	X			X		
<i>Gojek (GoTo)</i>	X				X	
<i>Graphhopper</i>	X				X	
<i>Interline Technologies</i>	X			X	X	
<i>Intevation</i>					X	
<i>Kontur</i>				X	X	
<i>MapToolkit</i>		X		X	X	
<i>Meta Platforms</i>	X	X	X	X	X	
<i>MobilityLabel</i>		X			X	
<i>OpenCage</i>	X			X		
<i>Plan4Better</i>			X		X	
<i>Protomaps</i>		X		X	X	
<i>Rinkai</i>	X	X			X	
<i>Stadia Maps</i>	X	X		X	X	
<i>StreetLight Data</i>			X		X	
<i>TEconecta</i>		X				X
<i>Thunderforest (Gravitystorm)</i>					X	
<i>TomTom</i>	X	X	X		X	
<i>VK</i>	X	X			X	

PM: policy maker, Pd: Producer, pv: provider, Br: Broker, VAR: value-added reseller, EU: end user.

As seen, big corporations tend to contribute in more diverse ways than small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), while SMEs generally prefer to focus their resources on a few ways of contribution. This makes sense considering the limited resources SMEs may have, preferring to contribute in the ways that benefit their business the most.

We also mapped the VGI-extended SDI stakeholder model (Cooper et al. 2011) to the interviewed companies. Companies that have a seat in the OSMF Advisory Board (OpenStreetMap Foundation 2024a) via their Corporate Membership are given the Policy Maker role. Those who add their own data to OSM are given the Producer role, and those who add derived data from their users (e.g. client reports, aggregated user data) or third parties are given the Provider role. Brokers are intermediaries that have services which allow their users to download data from OSM, or directly add data to it. Value-added resellers provide services with OSM data to an end user. End users are those internally using OSM data (e.g. for analysis).

Table 5 shows that the Value-added reseller (VAR) role is taken by the great majority of the companies interviewed. Commercial organizations tend, therefore, to provide a service to a customer enriched by OpenStreetMap data rather than being direct end users of the data. Other greatly undertaken roles are Policy Maker (PM), Producer (Pd), and Broker (Br). Finally, the least undertaken roles are Provider (Pv) and End user (EU).

4.3. Motivations for commercial organizations to contribute to the OSM ecosystem

Apart from how do they contribute, interviewees were also asked why are they contributing to OSM, with the results being available in Table 6.

The most and third most mentioned motivations are to improve the data quality and align with an own dataset.

Companies not only contribute to OSM but also use its data, and by contributing data, they are improving the quality of the services the company provides.

The second most mentioned motivation is to build a community. This motivation was mentioned in several contexts: mapping a given area or topic showing clients how to continue the work, kickstarting a local community on a given mapping topic, or organizing mapping events with local communities. These motivations show a desire to keep the edits the company both creates and needs to continue over time. It also pairs with the barrier mentioned by one company of lack of ground truth information. This barrier can be fixed by building local communities and empowering individuals with access to information on the ground.

SMEs also show motivations for the social value of their data contributions. These include being grateful and wanting to give back, being part of the 'open' movement, and believing OSM is an important service that should become sustainable.

Many companies mentioned data integration and tooling as the main barriers to data contribution. A lack of tooling to conflate two datasets or to handle the import of big datasets is mentioned as the problem. Better tools that use AI capabilities to improve the contribution were mentioned by an SME as a possible solution. The licence compatibility of the data companies have is also an issue for some of them, as they have aggregated data from different sources which they want to contribute, and OSM requires data added to the project to always come from open sources compatible with OSM Open Database Licence (ODbL) or to have specific permission from the data producer to be added into OSM.

SMEs see barriers in the lack of resources (funds, manpower, and time), in comparison with big corporations. This pairs with the ways they contribute (Table 4), where it can be seen that SMEs are focusing their contributions in the ways that would benefit their business the most,

Table 6. Motivations and barriers for contribution mentioned, ordered by most mentioned.

	Total Companies	Big Corp.	SMEs
Motivation			
To improve the data quality, in a source the company uses	8	5	3
To build a community	5	2	3
To align with an own dataset	4	2	2
Because we are grateful and want to give back	3	0	3
Because we are part of the 'open' movement	1	0	1
Because the project or client requires it	1	0	1
Because OSM is an important service	1	0	1
Barrier			
Data integration	4	2	2
Lack of tooling	3	1	2
Community pushback	3	3	0
License	3	2	1
Importing Guidelines	3	1	2
Lack of funds	3	0	3
Lack of manpower	2	0	2
Lack of time	2	0	2
Lack of ground truth info	1	0	1
Information on how to map for beginners	1	0	1

5. Discussion

Several limitations have been identified in the study, which are explained as follows. Companies often have OSM-driven employees who are an integral part of the overall OSM community on both personal and professional levels. Therefore, commercial entities and community members are often intertwined. As well, an employee's view may or may not represent the company's view as a whole.

Another identified limitation is the difficulty of finding companies that do not advertise themselves as users of or contributors to OSM. While OpenStreetMap Wiki (2024) and OpenStreetMap Foundation (2024b) were identified as lists of contributors, there can still be hidden contributors that do not document their commercial data editing or non-data value-adding. As well, no such detailed list exists for users of OSM data, and it remains a topic to explore.

Regarding the results of the study, we can see that commercial users mentioned several motivations to contribute to OSM that directly benefit their own businesses such as improving the data quality in a source the company uses, aligning with their own dataset, or because the project or client requires it. Additionally, there are motivations that may not offer immediate direct benefits but could indirectly or, in the long term, benefit commercial organizations.

OSM should aim to be a space where those own motivations are turned into values not only for the commercial users but also for the whole project and its sustainability as a public good. A balanced project where commercial users help keep the project alive with their value and financial contribution, but that is also inclusive of non-commercial stakeholders and their decision-making and value contribution, not falling onto the tragedy of the commons (Hardin 1968).

Several of the interviewed SMEs mentioned OSM as critical to their business, as they rely completely on their data for the services they provide. As seen on Table 5, companies mostly relate to the Value-added reseller (VAR) role in the SDI stakeholder model. OSM has, therefore, the potential to boost business cases by providing low-cost quality data and allowing commercial organizations to use their budget to develop a good service instead of acquiring data.

However, technical issues were still greatly mentioned on the data interoperability and data merging side. Future work is needed in this area, with the suggestion to encourage the creation of technical Communities of Practice (CoPs), to develop tools needed by several companies using shared resources. Such an example already exists in MapLibre (MapLibre 2024), and should be replicated further to continue fixing more technical barriers to the use of and contribution to OSM data.

The interviewees described the OSM community as both a strength and, for larger corporations, a potential barrier. As mentioned in the related work by Schrnder-Bergen et al., cooperation can lead to conflict when organizations fail to understand the local context and OSM dynamics. Some community members fear that the role of big corporations may become dominant, displacing the individual volunteer effort. A further investment of companies in not only data but overall value-creation, especially in the community-building realm, could help mitigate these tensions and enhance collaboration.

Lastly, although not reported by the interviewees, it has been noticed that most companies that currently advertise themselves as contributors to the project are tech-savvy. There is a lack of non-technical companies contributing to the project. The technical gap is to be reduced to align the private values of non-technical commercial organizations so they can contribute to the project. An example where this could happen is businesses updating their locations and contact details inside OpenStreetMap, making it widespread as it is currently in platforms like Google Maps. This would also benefit OSM in keeping updated points of interest in the map, a known lack of the project (Klinkhardt et al. 2023).

6. Conclusion and future work

This paper analysed how commercial organizations both use and contribute to OpenStreetMap (OSM) from interviews with employees of 25 organizations. The analysis of the interviews shows that most interviewed organizations use OSM data to enrich their services, which identifies them as Value-added resellers (VAR) in the SDI stakeholder roles. On the contribution side, five distinct contribution ways have been identified from the interviews: data editing, tool development and/or funding, event OSM Foundation or related funding, and community building. The motivations found are a mixture of own benefit and social value, and OSM should provide a space where those self-motivations can be turned into social good, while maintaining a barrier-free space that maintains project sustainability for all stakeholders. Finally, Overture Maps has been demonstrated to be a new development by commercial organizations that emerged as a response to OSM's barriers, but its effect on OSM is still early to measure.

In future work, collaboration between different stakeholders for mutual benefit has to be studied more in-depth, with specific examples, as this paper only gives an overview of them. Turksever (2024) explains such an example, where a local government body collaborates

with OpenStreetMap NGOs and two big corporations to keep the city pedestrian infrastructure up-to-date.

Measures to leverage the technical and governance barriers for non-technical commercial organizations to contribute are also to be studied, as this paper has shown a lack of non-tech-savvy organizations contributing value to OSM.

As well, studies on the effect Overture Maps can have in the commercial OSM ecosystem are expected in the following years, as the project grows in maturity.

Notes

1. StreetLight Data can be considered a SME until 2022, when it was bought by Jacobs.
2. Border data by United Nations available at <https://geoportal.un.org/arcgis/apps/sites/#/geohub/datasets/65e92c869dff4ea6865bd589e4e70703/>. The boundaries shown do not imply official endorsement or acceptance by the United Nations or the paper authors.
3. Data contribution to Daylight distribution (<https://daylightmap.org/>), but not to OSM itself
4. Allows employees to edit OSM during work time, at a private level.
5. The company is a one-person company, who maps as an individual.
6. Used to until 2 years ago, when they had a bad experience with the OSM Community.
7. Employee benefits for editing.
8. Used to before Covid and current geopolitical events, not anymore.

Disclosure statement

Author H. Ochoa-Ortiz has been an OpenStreetMap contributor on a personal level for years and has attended numerous OSM community events. Therefore, some of the individuals interviewed are H. Ochoa-Ortiz's personal contacts who were met through such events and were directly contacted to participate in the interview. Neither of the interviewed organizations has ever employed the authors, nor the authors have any direct commercial relation with them or any other competing interests. Valid at the time of submission. During the review phase of this paper, author H. Ochoa-Ortiz was appointed as a director at the OpenStreetMap Foundation (OSMF). The author does not represent the OSMF in this document.

Funding

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No [955569]. The opinions expressed in this document reflect only the authors' views and in no way reflect the European Commission's opinions. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

ORCID

Héctor Ochoa-Ortiz <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-6477-0683>
Barbara Re <http://orcid.org/0000-0001-5374-2364>

Data availability statement

The participants of this study did not give written consent for their data to be shared publicly, so due to the sensitive nature of the research supporting data is not available.

References

- Anderson, J. 2021. "Jennings Anderson's Diary | a 2021 Update on Paid Editing in OpenStreetMap." <https://www.openstreetmap.org/user/Jennings%20Anderson/diary/396271>.
- Anderson, J., and D. Sarkar. 2020. "Curious Cases of Corporations in OpenStreetMap." <http://2020.stateofthemap.org/sessions/SPRQVZ/>.
- Anderson, J., D. Sarkar, and L. Palen. 2019. "Corporate Editors in the Evolving Landscape of OpenStreetMap." *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information* 8 (5): 232. <https://www.mdpi.com/2220-9964/8/5/232>.
- Andreo, G. Spinoza, FM Welle Donker, and S. Calzati. 2023. "Assessing an open spatial data infrastructure from a user participation perspective: a qualitative exploratory research with openstreetmap." *International Conference on Open Data (ICOD 2022): Book of abstracts*, 124–128. Zagreb, Croatia. Faculty of Law, University of Zagreb. <https://zenodo.org/records/8073118>.
- Cazacu, S., R. Chandrasekhar, D. R. Melanie Dulong, and G. Vancauwenberghe. 2024. "User Needs from a Governance Perspective." *ODECO Deliverable D2.3*. https://odeco-research.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/ODECO-D2.3-User-needs-from-a-governance-perspective_Final.pdf.
- Cooper, A. K., S. Coetzee, H. Moellering, P. Rapant, J. Cromptvoets, J. Hjelmager, T. Delgado, A. Iwaniak, and I. Kaczmarek. 2023. "A Review of the ICA Model of Stakeholders in a Spatial Data Infrastructure (SDI)." *Advances in Cartography and GIScience of the ICA* 4:1–8. Publisher: Copernicus GmbH, Available from: <https://ica-adv.copernicus.org/articles/4/5/2023/>.
- Cooper, Antony K., Petr Rapant, Jan Hjelmager, Dominique Laurent, Adam Iwaniak, Serena Coetzee, Harold Moellering, and Ulrich Düren. 2011. "Extending the Formal Model of a Spatial Data Infrastructure to Include Volunteered Geographical Information." *Proceedings of the 25th International Cartographic Conference (ICC 2011)*, July. <http://hdl.handle.net/10204/5212>.

- Goodchild, M. F. 2007. "Citizens as Sensors: The World of Volunteered Geography." *Geo Journal* 69 (4): 211–221. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10708-007-9111-y>.
- Grinberger, A. Y., M. Minghini, L. Juhász, G. Yeboah, and P. Mooney. 2022. "OSM Science—The Academic Study of the OpenStreetMap Project, Data, Contributors, Community, and Applications." *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information* 11 (4): 230. <https://www.mdpi.com/2220-9964/11/4/230>.
- Grinberger, A. Yair, Hao Liu, Pengyuan Liu, Godwin Yeboah, Levente Juhász, Serena Coetzee, Peter Mooney, Alessandro Sarretta, Jennings Anderson, and Marco Minghini. 2023. "OpenStreetMap as an Emerging Scientific Field: Reflections from OSM Science 2023." *Proceedings of the OSM Science at State of the Map Europe 2023*, Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/records/10443298>.
- Hardin, G. 1968. "The Tragedy of the Commons." *Science* 162 (3859): 1243–1248. <https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/science.162.3859.1243>.
- Jamshed, S. 2014. "Qualitative Research Method-Interviewing and Observation." *Journal of Basic and Clinical Pharmacy* 5 (4): 87. Publisher: Wolters Kluwer – Medknow Publications, Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4194943/>.
- Klinkhardt, C., F. Kühnel, M. Heilig, S. Lautenbach, T. Wörle, P. Vortisch, and T. Kuhnimhof. 2023. "Quality Assessment of OpenStreetMap's Points of Interest with Large-Scale Real Data." *Transportation Research Record: Journal of the Transportation Research Board* 2677 (12): 661–674. <https://doi.org/10.1177/03611981231169280>.
- MapLibre. 2024. "Sponsors." <https://maplibre.org/sponsors/>.
- Michel, B., and S. Schröder-Bergen. 2022. *The Politics of Geodata in Urban Platform Capitalism*. Transcript Verlag, <https://www.degruyter.com/document/doi/10.1515/9783839459645-005/html>.
- Office of Management and Budget. 2002. "Circular No. A-16, Revised." https://georgewbush-whitehouse.archives.gov/omb/circulars/a016/print/a016_rev.html#background.
- OpenStreetMap Foundation. 2024a. "Advisory Board - OpenStreetMap Foundation." https://osmfoundation.org/wiki/Advisory_Board.
- OpenStreetMap Foundation. 2024b. "Corporate Members - OpenStreetMap Foundation." https://osmfoundation.org/wiki/Corporate_Members.
- OpenStreetMap Wiki. 2023. "Foundation — OpenStreetMap Wiki." [Online]. Accessed February 6, 2024. <https://wiki.openstreetmap.org/w/index.php?title=Foundation&oldid=2618476>.
- OpenStreetMap Wiki. 2024. "Organised Editing/Activities — OpenStreetmap Wiki." [Online]. Accessed February 7, 2024. https://wiki.openstreetmap.org/w/index.php?title=Organised_Editing/Activities&oldid=2656488.
- Overture Maps Foundation. 2024. "Introduction | Overture Maps Documentation." <https://docs.overturemaps.org/>.
- Park, C. H., J. Longo, and E. W. Johnston. 2020. "Exploring Non-State Stakeholder and Community-Led Open Governance: Beyond the Three Pillars of Open Government." *Public Performance & Management Review* 43 (3): 587–612. Publisher: Routledge. eprint: <https://doi.org/10.1080/15309576.2019.1677253>.
- Pollet, M. 2022. "EU Task Force Calls for Digital Commons Foundation Launch." Section: Technology. <https://www.euractiv.com/section/digital/news/eu-task-force-calls-for-digital-commons-foundation-launch/>.
- Sarkar, D., and J. T. Anderson. 2022. "Corporate Editors in OpenStreetMap: Investigating Co-Editing Patterns." *Transactions in GIS* 26 (4): 1879–1897. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/tgis.12910>.
- Schröder-Bergen, S., G. Glasze, B. Michel, and F. Dammann. 2022. "De/Colonizing OpenStreetMap? Local Mappers, Humanitarian and Commercial Actors and the Changing Modes of Collaborative Mapping." *Geo Journal* 87 (6): 5051–5066. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10708-021-10547-7>.
- Schröder-Bergen, Susanne. 2023. "Social, Technical and Political Transformations in OpenStreetMap – from Volunteered Geographic Information to Embedding Digital Commons in Platform Capitalism." *Proceedings of the OSM Science at State of the Map Europe 2023*, Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/records/10443321>.
- Spinoza Andreo, G. 2022. *Assessing an Open Spatial Data Infrastructure from a User Participation Perspective: A Qualitative Exploratory Research of OpenStreetMap*. Thesis (Masters), TU Delft Architecture and the Built Environment. <http://resolver.tudelft.nl/uuid:7fda6562-5018-4c46-8fe8-4e6c34a70eb6>.
- Turkseven, S. 2024. "Streamlining Data Improvement and Quality Check for Pedestrian Map Data on OpenStreetMap: Milano Case Study." <https://cfp.openstreetmap.org/pl/state-of-the-map-europe-2024/talk/XUZA7X/>.
- Vancauwenberghe, G., and B. van Loenen. 2018. "Exploring the Emergence of Open Spatial Data Infrastructures: Analysis of Recent Developments and Trends in Europe." In *User Centric E-Government: Challenges and Opportunities. Integrated Series in Information Systems*, edited by S. Saeed, T. Ramayah, and Z. Mahmood, 23–45. Cham: Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-59442-2_2.
- Veselovsky, V., D. Sarkar, J. Anderson, and R. Soden. 2022. "An Automated Approach to Identifying Corporate Editing." *Proceedings of the International AAAI Conference on Web and Social Media*, 1052–1063. Vol. 16. <https://ojs.aaai.org/index.php/ICWSM/article/view/19357>.
- Yang, A., H. Fan, Q. Jia, M. Ma, Z. Zhong, J. Li, and N. Jing. 2024. "How Do Contributions of Organizations Impact Data Inequality in OpenStreetMap?" *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems* 109:102077. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0198971524000061>.

Appendix

Interview questions

- Name
- Role in organization
- Organization name
- Describe the nature and function of your organization
- Does your organization use geospatial Open Data in its daily operations? How?
- Which sources of Geospatial Open Data do you use?
- Do you also use non-open sources? Which?
- How easy is it to find these data sources?
- Does your organization use OpenStreetMap? How?
- Does your organization contribute to OSM? Why? How? (it can also be non-data contributions to the OSM ecosystem)
- What is the motivation for your organization to contribute to OSM?
- Are there any barriers to the contribution?
- Do you consider your organization to be more towards the user or the producer side of OSM data? Why?
- Do you release Open Geospatial Data somewhere else than OSM? Why?
- Can you describe the main strengths and weaknesses of OSM?
- Do you have contact with other stakeholders in the OSM Ecosystem? With whom?
- Does your organization try to engage stakeholders in some way?
- How would you improve stakeholder engagement in OSM?
- What would you improve about OSM in general?
- Does your organization have any specific goals within OSM?
- How would you describe your average user/client for your data/product/service?
- Do you have a target user/client?
- How many users do your data/products/services have? (estimation)
- Does this number include only OSM-based products?
- Do you use any specific technology stack to handle geospatial data, including OSM?
- Does your organization use AI technologies with geospatial data?
- Other comments
- Do you suggest we contact someone else for this interview?